

FACTORS AFFECTING TEACHERS' TEACHING PERFORMANCE IN LIBORAN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL, BAUNGON DISTRICT IN THE DIVISION OF BUKIDNON

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Abstract: This study primarily determined the influence of the factors affecting teachers' teaching performance in Liboran Elementary School, Baungon District 1 in the Division of Bukidnon. It specifically, it sought to answer the following questions: What is the extent of factors affecting the teachers' teaching performance in Liboran Elementary School in Baungon 1 District in the Division of Bukidnon? 1. What is the extent of factors affecting the teachers' teaching performance in Liboran Elementary School in Baungon 1 District in the Division of Bukidnon? 2. What is the level of teachers' teaching performance when they are categorized as; Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Unsatisfactory, and poor. 3.) Is there a significant relationship between the level of teachers' teaching performance and the extent of factors affecting teachers' teaching performance in Liboran Elementary School in Baungon 1 District in the Division of Bukidnon?

Keywords: Factors Affecting Teachers' Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Teachers play a very crucial role in the holistic development of every Filipino learner. They have to ensure that learners are engaged and motivated, to help them acquire knowledge and develop understanding, to enable them to demonstrate their knowledge and understanding through performance and action, to encourage them to engage in critical reflection of the world and their place within it, to develop their ability to navigate the constraints and complexities of the world in formulating their own judgements and designs for action and to foster a lifelong commitment to critical examination and self-development.

The framework of the study is anchored on **RA 10533** which is known as the "Enhanced Basic Education of 2013" and **DepEd Order No. 36, s.2013** which stipulates the role of teachers in nation building. Through quality teachers, the Philippines can develop holistic learners who are steeped in values, equipped with 21st century skills, and able to propel the country to development and progress. This is in consonance with the DepEd's vision of producing Filipino who passionately love their country and whose values and competencies enable them to realize their full potential and contribute meaningfully to building the nation.

Further, it emphasizes that teachers undeniably are vibrant to raising students' achievement such as quality learning is contingent upon quality teaching. Hence, enhancing teachers' quality and instructional task performance are of utmost importance for long-term and sustainable nation building.

The relevance of teachers' teaching performance is the basic consideration for assuring quality pupils' learning outcomes in the school organization. Harvey (2019) pointed out that quality teaching as the process of ensuring effective resource input, control, refining the standards of output in order to meet the set goals and satisfy public accountability. In the context of Philippine education delivery, Calaguas (2018) described there are factors that influence teacher's teaching performance such as the school head's systematic management, monitoring and evaluation of performance by the school administrators, teachers and students against educational goals to ensure consistent documentation, review and decision towards quality improvement in institutional management, and teaching and learning processes for the achievement of set of standards in schools.

Casañero (2018) espoused that teachers' teaching performance is associated with socio-demographic factors such as attitude towards teaching, the number of years in the teaching profession, personal motivation in teaching, educational preparation, and professional upgrading such as attendance to trainings and seminar workshops. Additionally, teaching performance is also attributed to teachers' instructional responsibility in order to affect pupils' learning outcomes. However, it was also emphasized that to ensure quality learning outcomes the school heads should consistently encourage, motivate, and monitor teachers' performance and ensure that they complied with the school's standards.

In a similar investigation, Herrera (2019) claimed that teachers' teaching performance effectiveness is evidenced on efficient and effective classroom management, teaching delivery, evaluation and reviews of the teaching and learning transformation process to produce quality learning outputs.

Labadia (2018) revealed that effectiveness of teachers' performance is the result of factors such professional commitment to the teaching profession and the desire to help students to learn, personal satisfaction with their work which typically display higher levels of motivated behavior and performance as well as lower levels of work anxiety and burnout.

The Department of Education regularly evaluates teachers' teaching performance in order to ensure instructional quality and achievements of institutional objectives. However, the gap between teaching performance and achievement of instructional and institutional goals still exists. It is in this context that the researcher is motivated to conduct this study to find out the factors that influence teachers' teaching performance especially in Liboran Elementary School, Baungon 1 District, in the Division of Bukidnon.

2. THEORETICAL/CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The concept of the study is anchored on the study of **Casañero (2018)** who pointed out that teachers' teaching performance is associated with socio-demographic factors such as attitude towards teaching, the number of years in the teaching profession, personal motivation in teaching, educational preparation, and professional upgrading such as attendance to trainings and seminar workshops.

The paradigm of the study is anchored on the **Social Constructivist Theory** by Lev Vygotsky (1978). Social constructivism is a sociological theory of knowledge according to which human development is socially situated and knowledge is constructed through interaction with others. Like social constructionism, social constructivism states that people work together to construct knowledge.

Campbell (2018) and Burns, et al (2017) indicated that teachers are essential for the effectiveness and improvement of school. They purported that in educational contexts, spreading positivity and goodwill, helping new colleagues, staying after school to tutor students, and voicing concerns in areas that may be detrimental to school, ability to manifests skills and competences in teaching an learning process, or making constructive suggestions that may benefit schools are some of the examples of task performance.

Lopez, et al (2018) claimed that teachers' teaching performance and instructional tasks are extra-role functions that are performed by the teachers to enable learners achieve the set educational goals in schools. This ultimately depends on the avowed commitment of teachers to make appropriate utilization of human and material resources to ensure quality assurance in the teaching-learning process.

Further, it was exemplified that teachers' teaching performance is a manifestation of teachers' ability to demonstrate sound professional attributes like scholarship through appropriate and sufficient pedagogical trainings needed and necessary for successful teaching, students' learning outcomes and achievement of quality education in the public schools.

In a similar study, Bello, et al (2019) pointed out that students' learning outcomes and attainment of quality education is predictive of teachers' quality which is manifested in their knowledge of the subject matter, skills and competences in the teaching and learning processes, which leads to the accomplishments of the stated educational goals and objectives. This implies that the real teachers possess the qualities for effective teaching, know what they are teaching, how to teach, and for whom they are teaching.

Additionally, it was pointed out that teachers need to deliver the curriculum efficiently, so as to achieve the set goals and standards in schools (Koleoso, 2016; Makinde & Alao, 2017). The teachers' role is crucial to effective and efficient learning, the teacher is expected to provide essential inputs like adequate planning of lesson notes, effective delivery of lessons, proper monitoring and evaluation of students' performance, providing regular feed-back on students' performance, improvisation of instructional materials, adequate keeping of records and appropriate discipline of students to produce and enhance expected learning achievement in school.

The conceptual framework of the study suggests the parameters wherein it ascertain the relationship between the predictive variables or factors and the teachers' teaching performance. The conceptual model in figure 1 shows the interplay between the dependent and the independent variables of the study.

Schema of the Study

Figure 1 Schematic diagram showing the interplay between the dependent and independent variables

3. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The study aimed to assess the factors affecting the teachers' teaching performance in Liboran Elementary School in Baungon 1 District in the Division of Bukidnon.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

- 1.) What is the extent of factors affecting the teachers' teaching performance in Liboran Elementary School in Baungon 1 District in the Division of Bukidnon?
- 2.) What is the level of teachers' teaching performance when they are categorized as;
 - 2.1. Outstanding
 - 2.2. Very Satisfactory

2.3. Satisfactory

2.4. Unsatisfactory

2.5. Poor

3.) Is there a significant relationship between the level of teachers' teaching performance and the extent of factors affecting teachers' teaching performance in Liboran Elementary School in Baungon 1 District in the Division of Bukidnon?

Research Hypothesis

Problems 1 and 2 are hypotheses free. Problem 3 was tested at 0.05 level of significance, where the hypothesis will be stated in a null form:

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between the level of teachers' teaching performance and the extent of factors affecting teachers' teaching performance in Liboran Elementary School in Baungon 1 District in the Division of Bukidnon.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study utilizes the descriptive research design. Descriptive research according to Calderon, et al (2012) is a fact-finding inquiry or investigation. It was employed to develop a thorough knowledge of the primary causes of the given situations.

In addition, descriptive design as an inquiry used an in-depth analysis of the problem which data collection methods include, but not limited to the survey questionnaire and the like.

Subsequently, descriptive research design will be utilized to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. This method measures variables through the use of quantifiable or finite data and the analysis will be based on generated information from statistical tools. This method was also used in an inquiry with larger population.

Successively, descriptive data gathering procedures comprise different types of gathering information such as, but not limited to, the use of adapted survey questionnaires.

5. FINDINGS

The following findings were summarized as follows:

1. By and large, the respondents **occasionally** apply an authoritarian style of classroom management. On one hand, they **frequently** expect high discipline to maintain order. On the contrary, the respondents **never** make sure his rules are strictly adhered to. In terms of democratic classroom management style, the respondents **always** apply the latter. They **always** concern of meeting their pupils' needs, develop plan to help the pupils evaluate their performance, and appreciate the opinion of the pupils. The findings showed that the respondents **always** care about the wellness of the pupils. Upon the other side, the respondents **never** apply laissez faire style in classroom management. Similarly, they described as **never** that the teacher does not show concern about pupils' personal problem. Further, they described as **never** that the teacher does not give rule in the classroom.
2. Majority of the pupil respondents obtained a **very satisfactory** level of learning achievements. Contrarywise, only few obtained a **satisfactory** level of pupils' learning achievements.
3. The classroom management style in terms of authoritarian shows **negligible correlation** to the level of pupils' learning achievement as the probability value showed no significance. Further, democratic classroom management style shows **negligible correlation** to the learning achievement of the pupils as indicated by no significant probability value. On one hand, laissez faire style shows **moderate correlation** to the learning achievement as indicated by the probability value means significant.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings, this study came up with the following conclusions:

1. The extent of classroom management style of the select teachers of San Miguel Elementary School in terms of authoritarian is moderate. The teacher usually dictates policies and procedures and direct and control all activities in the classroom. They rarely expect outmost disciplinary action for orderliness. On one hand, the teachers are so lenient in imposing rules in classroom. In terms of democratic style, the teachers are constantly applied freedom and independency of their students. Similarly, the teachers are constantly concerning the meeting of pupils' needs, developing plan to guide the students, and appreciating them regularly. They regularly check the wellness of their pupils. In terms of laissez faire style, the teachers do not impose policies and guidelines in contravene to the classroom management policy. Additionally, the teacher never disregards the essential concern of the pupils. Upon the other side, the teachers are not irresponsible in giving proper instructions to their pupils.
2. Most pupils in San Miguel Elementary School are very good in accomplishing their output and performance based on the level of competency. Contrarywise, only few of the select pupils got an average rating of their learning achievement.
3. It can be concluded that authoritarian leadership styles and learning achievements were not correlated. Therefore, there are still many ways to improve learning performance and applying authoritarian style does not in any way affect the performance of the students. The learning achievements are not significantly influenced by democratic leadership styles. On the other hand, the learning achievements are significantly influence by laissez faire style of classroom management.

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